

APPLICABILITY OF A TAPPING METHOD TO NON-DESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) will be widely used to manufacture autobodies in order to lighten the whole weight of automobiles owing to their higher specific modulus and strength. Compared with carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resins (CFRTS), carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have significant advantages of short molding time, low processing cost and excellent recyclability. Unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (UD-CFRTP), ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (UT-CTT) and carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastics (CMT) are being developed specifically for high-volume production of lightweight automobiles. Therefore non-destructive inspection (NDI) will become indispensable for mass manufacturing and application of CFRTP automotive parts. In this paper, as one of the most common NDI methods, tapping method was introduced to check the health condition and detect defects such as voids caused by inadequate molding or inappropriate use of CFRTP parts. Voids and delamination are the most common defects generated inside of CFRTP components. Upgraded tapping methods including both global method and local method were utilized to inspect CFRTP plates. The instrumented hammer with a force transducer built into its head was designed to tap specimen lightly. Force transducer, microphone and accelerometer were adopted to acquire signals, respectively. A simplified spring-damping model was proposed to describe the physical mechanism of defect detection. The contact duration of defective region was longer than that of sound region, and the peak of interactive force applied on defective region was lowered owing to local stiffness degradation which made modal frequencies of the specimen decrease. The damping capacity of defective plate increased in view of the additional energy dissipation caused by internal defects. Because the tapping test has limitation of defect depth, the sensitivity of defect identification decreases markedly with the depth of defect increasing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resins (CFRTS) are extensively used in many industrial areas, on account of their high specific modulus and strength. Different from traditional unidirectional CFRTS (UD-CFRTS), discontinuous CFRTS are superiority of outstanding molding performance and flexible designability for complex structures. In recent decades, many researchers are engaging in reducing the weight of automobiles by using discontinuous CFRTS [1-7].

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have been brought to the research forefront due to their significant advantages of molding time, manufacturing cost, recyclability and so on [8-9]. In Japan, a long term national project is being supported to carry out high-volume production of lightweight automobile [10-11]. Current research all over the world is being aimed at substituting metal parts for CFRTP parts under the condition of maintaining or improving the mechanical performance of the relevant structures [12-13]. In this research, unidirectional CFRTP (UD-CFRTP), ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (UT-CTT) and carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastics (CMT) were used since they are now being developed specifically to replace metal auto parts.

Health monitoring and damage detection of mass CFRP components production will be gradually prominent because of rapid development and mass application of CFRP in automotive industry. Many kinds of internal defects such as voids, porosities are easily generated during improper molding due to the particularity of meso-structures and manufacturing process of CFRP. Cracks,

delamination and barely visible impact damage (BVID) are also common flaws caused by collision. An extensive amount of research has been carried out to analyse the cause of defects inside of CFRP [14-17]. Because non-destructive inspection (NDI) technologies don't introduce additional destruction during inspection process, NDI plays a non-substitutable role in the field of defect detection [18-22].

Ultrasonic testing (UT) is limited by narrow frequency range caused by the high attenuation of CFRP. Radiographic test (RT) has the worst safety profile. Shearography can only be applied to specimens with smooth surface and near-surface flaws. Acoustic emission (AE) will introduce additional defects to generate the acoustic signal. Different from the inspection methods mentioned above, coin-tap test [23-30] is the most convenient NDI method, and has already been extensively used to inspect damages inside of structures and materials. Peter Cawley [31-34], John Summerscales [35], and Sung Joon Kim [36-39] proposed simplified mechanical model and conducted lots of verification tests around tapping test.

In this paper, an upgraded tapping method divided into global method and local method was adopted to inspect internal defects. It was the first time to conduct feasibility study of tapping method for flaws inside of CFRTP. A small impact hammer with a built-in force transducer in its head was employed to tap the specimens lightly, force transducer, microphone and accelerometer were used to acquire signals. For global method, compared with the pre-destructive specimen, the modal damping of post-destructive specimen augmented slightly, the modal frequency of post-destructive specimen decreased markedly. For local method, the peak of interactive force applied on defective area was lower than that of sound area, the contact duration of interactive force over defective area was longer than that of sound area. The sensitivity of local detection decreased with the depth of delamination or resin-rich area increasing.

2 MATERIAL MANUFACTURE AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Raw CFRTP and CFRTS material

Raw CMT material was provided by Toray Industries, Inc., raw UD-CFRTP material was provided by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd., raw UT-CTT material was provided by Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. UD-CFRTP and UD-CFRTS specimens (Figure 1 (a)) were molded by unidirectional carbon fiber prepregs. UT-CTT specimens (Figure 1 (b)) were composed of extensive amount of unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg tapes whose dimension is $18 \times 5 \times 0.04$ mm. Short fibers (6 mm length) inside of CMT specimens were dispersed randomly within the thin CMT plate (Figure 1 (c)).

(a) Unidirectional specimen

(b) UT-CTT specimen

(c) CMT specimen

Figure 1: Schematic diagrams for CFRTP and CFRTS specimens.

2.2 CFRTP and CFRTS specimens with defects

In this research, specimens with common defects (ex. delamination, voids and resin-rich zone) were fabricated by hot compression molding process. The detail information of materials used in this study was listed in the Table 1. Some CMT specimens with different volume fraction (V_f) of carbon fiber (V_f 10%, 20% and 30%) were molded under 4 MPa. Some CMT (V_f 20%) specimens were molded under 0.03 MPa, 0.5 MPa and 2.0 MPa, respectively. Due to the lower molding pressure (≤ 2.0 MPa), quantities of voids were generated in CMT specimens. Non-sticky Teflon thin-films were filled between UD-CFRTP prepregs or CMT sheets to generate artificial delaminations, respectively. The size and depth of artificial delamination were different from each other. The dimension of Teflon film laid through transverse direction of the specimen (Figure 2 (a)) was $100 \times 125 \times 0.2$ mm. Due to the ample size and non-sticky performance of Teflon film, the delamination defect was generated. The dimension of Teflon film laid through longitudinal direction of the specimen (Figure 2 (b)) was $10 \times 250 \times 0.2$ mm. Because

the slender film was molded between CMT sheets under high molding pressure (4MPa), this defect was regarded as resin-rich defect. According to the reference [35], delaminations inside of UT-CTT and UD-CFRP specimens were generated by applying tensile load on both ends of the L-shaped specimens. And the size of delaminations inside of them was controlled through adjusting tensile load.

Table 1 Material information.

Material type	Resin	Vf	CF length	Delamination	Voids	Resin-rich zone
UD-CFRTS	epoxy	60%	continuous	√	×	×
UD-CFRTP	PP	45%	continuous	√	×	×
UT-CTT	PA6	50%	18mm	√	×	×
CMT	PP	10%, 20%, 30%	6mm	√	√	√

(a) Delamination (red region)

(b) Resin-rich (red region)

Figure 2: Defects location by ultrasonic inspection (blue region stand for sound region).

2.3 Experimental procedure

Both local method and global method were adopted to inspect the specimens in this study. As for global method, the specimen was suspended by thin nylon filament (Figure 3 (a)), the whole structure responses including resonant frequency and damping were analyzed to evaluate its health condition. Local method focused on the peak and contact duration of interactive force profile, because the force transducer could only acquire signal from the local tapping area of the specimen. The specimen was placed on the horizontal table surface, the input force was adjusted by controlling the dropping height of hammer (Figure 3 (b), (c)).

(a) Global method

(b) Local method (overall)

(c) Local method (partial)

Figure 3: Experimental setups for tapping method.

3 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

3.1 Assessment indexes of global method

Modal frequency and damping are the main parameters used to evaluate the health condition of specimen. According to vibration theory, modulus of CFRP plate with uniform cross section (ex.

rectangular, circular) is proportional to the square of modal frequency (Figure 4 (a)) of longitudinal, transverse or torsional vibrations. The wider 3 dB band width 2δ (Figure 4 (b)) or higher attenuation coefficient $\zeta\omega_n$ of a signal mode (Figure 4 (c)) mean higher damping property. Because of modulus reduction caused by the existence of defect, the modal frequencies of post-destructive specimen were lower than those of pre-destructive specimen. The attenuation coefficients of post-destructive specimen were higher since the delamination, voids or resin-rich areas absorbed more energy during vibration.

(a) Frequency spectrum analysis (b) Damping derived from 3dB band (c) Attenuation of a single mode

Figure 4: Modal frequency and damping analysis for specimen.

3.2 Theoretical model for local method

The detection mechanism of local tapping method was illustrated in the Figure 5 (a). Due to the existence of dampening effect of specimen, the damped simple harmonic motion (DSHM) system (Figure 5 (c)) was proposed to describe the inspection behavior. As shown in the Equation (1), (2) derived from the DSHM modal, the stiffness k_d of delaminated area is remarkably lower than the stiffness k_c of sound area, thus the measured stiffness k_e of two springs in series was lower than either of them. The relationship between contact duration and local stiffness were expressed in the Equation (3). The input forces were kept the same for both the defective and sound areas. As revealed in the Figure 6 (a), the peak of interactive force applied on defective area was lower than that of sound area, but the contact duration of interactive force profile over defective area was longer than that of sound area. The frequency spectrum graph of sound area decreased faster than that of defective area (Figure 6 (b)) after processing force data by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

(a) Schematic diagram for local method

(b) Damped simple harmonic motion model

Figure 5: Simplified theoretical model for local tapping method.

$$\frac{1}{k_d} + \frac{1}{k_c} = \frac{1}{k_e} \quad (1)$$

$$k_e < k_c \quad (2)$$

$$T = \pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{k}} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{T_1}{T_2} = \sqrt{\frac{m_1}{m_2}} \quad (4)$$

(a) Interactive force profile of local tapping method (b) Spectrum analysis of local interactive force
Figure 6: Interactive force analysis for local method.

3.3 Force-time curve analysis

As demonstrated in figure 7 (a), the real deformation of the cantilever beam was constituted of many modes. The same went for the deformation of NDI specimens, many modes of whom were excited by tapping. Thus the curve of force-time was not strictly sine curve, which was shown in the figure 7 (b). The descending grade of latter part of the curve decreased slowly, which was fit with the cubic curve.

(a) Simplified mode analysis for cantilever beam (b) Curve fitting for interactive force profile
Figure 7: Deformation analysis for specimens and curve fitting for interactive force profile

4 RESULTS

4.1 Tapping method (global method)

Global inspection focused on modal damping and frequency analysis for defective and sound specimens. All CMT specimens detected by global method were molded with the same amount of CMT sheets (V_f 20%). For CMT specimens (Figure 2) molded under the same pressure (4 MPa), the attenuation coefficients of them were nearly the same despite the presence of defects (resin-rich zone or delamination). But the corresponding modal frequencies of defective specimens were a little smaller than those of sound specimen (Figure 8). Especially for specimen with large delaminated area, the higher modal frequencies were ambiguous. For CMT specimens molded under lower pressures, voids volume fraction were 2.1% (2 MPa), 22.9% (0.5 MPa) and 48.3% (0.03 MPa), respectively. The attenuation coefficients increased significantly for higher modes (ex. mode 2, 3). The modal frequencies (Figure 9 (b)) were also markedly different mainly because of the different thicknesses (thickness 2.18 mm, thickness 1.96 mm). Moreover, when the voids ratio was lower than 2.0%, modal frequencies of these specimens (Figure 9 (c)) were nearly same.

Figure 8: Damping and frequency analysis for CMT specimens with different defects.

Figure 9: Damping and frequency analysis for CMT specimens molded under different pressures.

For the same specimen, frequency spectrum analyses were conducted before and after destruction. As shown in the Figure 10, modal frequencies significantly decreased when delamination inside of UT-CTT specimen occurred. If large delaminated area or specimen breakage occurred, the higher modal frequencies were unclear as shown in the Figure 10 (b).

Figure 10: Frequency spectrum analysis for UT-CTT specimens (before and after destruction).

4.3 Tapping method (local method)

Compared with global method, local method only paid close attention to the local area. The contact duration and peak of force profile were the main parameters measured during tapping inspection. In order to validate the accuracy of simplified theoretical model for defect inspection, several possible influencing factors were considered first. The weight of hammer was adjusted from 3.7 g to 12.8 g by affixing additional mass. Taking UD-CFRTP specimens for example, contact duration was extended with the weight of hammer increasing (Figure 11).

(a) Weight of hammer (3.7 g)

(b) Weight of hammer (12.8 g)

Figure 11: The influence of weight of hammer on contact duration.

In order to clarify the relationship between contact duration and impact velocity, the weight of hammer is fixed (8 g). The impact velocity of hammer was adjusted through controlling the dropping height. As shown in Figure 12 (a), (b), different force profiles with different peaks of impact forces had the same contact durations, no matter the tapping region was sound or delaminated area.

(a) Sound area of UD-CFRTP

(b) Delamination inside of UD-CFRTP

Figure 12: The influence of impact velocity and constraint condition on force profile.

CMT specimens with different depths of resin-rich or delaminated area were inspected by local method. The attention was paid to first wave shape of force-time curve (Figure 13 (a), (b)), especially the contact duration and peak of the interactive force profile, which had significant difference between sound and defective area. The sensitivity of defect identification decreased with the depth increasing. As shown in the Figure 13 (c), the peak of tapping force applied on CMT specimen (Vf 10%) was a little lower than those of CMT specimens (Vf 20%, 30%). The contact duration of CMT specimen (Vf 10%) was a little longer than those of CMT specimens (Vf 20%, 30%). Lower molding pressures resulted in higher volume fraction of voids inside of CMT specimens. When the void ratio was lower than 2% (2.0 MPa), local method couldn't give an excellent sensitivity of void detection.

Figure 13: Defect inspection for CMT specimens

UD-CFRTP specimens with different delamination depths were inspected by local method. For delamination ($5 \times 5 \times 0.1$ mm) at a depth of 0.66 mm, its contact duration was nearly same with that of sound area, but its peak of force profile was markedly different with that of sound area. When the delamination located at a depth of 1.43 mm, delamination with dimension of $5 \times 5 \times 0.1$ mm could not be detected by local method, delamination with dimension of $15 \times 15 \times 0.1$ mm could be inspected.

Figure 14: Inspection for UD-CFRTPS specimens with different delamination depths

5 DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Analysis of global method

Generally, lower molding pressure lead to lower modulus and higher void ratio for CFRTP specimens. According to vibration theory, modulus is positively correlated with modal frequencies of rectangular or circular beam. Inversely, modal frequencies could be used to elevate the real-time modulus of CFRTP beam. In this research, frequency resolution of signal acquired from accelerometer were higher than those acquired from microphone due to the influence of ambient noise and the lower signal intensity of some modal frequencies. For the same specimen, the modal frequencies of post-destructive specimen were lower than those of pre-destructive specimen owing to the modulus reduction caused by defect. For different CFRTP plates (the same length and width) molded with the same amount

of raw material, lower frequency didn't always indicate lower modulus. Because different molding pressures led to different thicknesses which had great influence on the modal frequencies. Especially for complex CFRTP structure, frequency spectrum analysis were difficult to inspect small internal defect.

Many kinds of damping mechanisms (ex. viscoelastic damping, thermoelastic damping, and coulomb friction) were responsible for excellent vibration attenuation ability of CFRTP material themselves. Thus attenuation coefficient of CMT specimens didn't increase markedly despite the presence of big size defects (resin-rich, delamination or voids). For the same CMT specimen, the attenuation coefficients augmented significantly as the mode number increased. Based on the modal damping estimated by 3 dB band method, the damping property of post-destructive UT-CTT specimen enhanced considerably compared with pre-destructive UT-CTT specimen. Similar with frequency spectrum analysis above, modal damping analysis also confronted the difficulty in mode identification for complex structure. Furthermore, only overall evaluation of CFRTP specimens could be obtained, both modal frequency and damping analysis couldn't locate the defective area inside of CFRTP.

5.2 Analysis of local method

According to equation (3), the contact duration was proportional to square root of weight of hammer. The contact duration was changed when the weight of instrumented hammer correspondingly was adjusted. When the weight of hammer was 3.7 g, contact duration of sound and delaminated areas were around 0.155 and 0.205 millisecond, respectively. When the weight of hammer was 12.8 g, contact duration of sound and delaminated areas were around 0.29 and 0.38 millisecond, separately. This is, the equation (4) was validated by these test data.

As the test results showed above, whether sound or delaminated areas, the contact durations were nearly the same under different impact velocities within 1.5 m/s, which indicated the impact velocity had no influence on contact duration. When only contact duration was considered, the impact velocity needn't be kept the same for the same hammer.

5.3 Sensitivity of CFRTP and CFRTS

In this research, it was the first time to inspect CFRTP specimens by both local method and global method. Overall, the sensitivities of defect identification between CFRTP and CFRTS specimens were nearly same. Different types of CFRTP were inclined to different defects. The most common defect of CMT material was internal void which could be detected by tapping method when void ratio was higher than 2.0%. The large resin-rich area (10 × 10 mm) inside of CMT specimen could also be identified by local method. Tapping method had limitation of inspection for unobvious and relative resin-rich zone where the difference of carbon fiber volume fraction was small (Figure 13 (c)). The most easily produced defect inside of UT-CTT, UD-CFRTP and UD-CFRTS specimen was delamination. With the depth of delamination or resin-rich region increasing, the sensitivity of local method would decrease due to the increasing local stiffness of defective area. If the width of delamination gap (depth 1.5 mm) was less than 0.05 mm, it could not be inspected.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an optimized tapping method device was designed to inspect common defects inside of CFRTP for the first time. The applicability of both global method and local method were verified for defecting delamination, resin-rich and voids. For simple structure like plate, global method could be used to evaluate the health condition of CFRP specimen by comparing the modal frequencies and damping properties before and after destruction. This study showed that the weight of hammer was proportional to the square of contact duration of interactive force. While the impact velocity of hammer didn't influence the contact duration. The interactive force profile was influenced by many modal shapes excited by tapping. As a result of that, the force-time curve was not strict sine curve. The peak and contact duration of force profile were significantly different from those of sound area due to loss of local stiffness. The accuracy of defect identification would decrease significantly with the defect size decreasing as well as the increasing depth.

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